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THE KHOJALY TRAGEDY ON THE THEATER SCENE

Abstract. The subject of the article was the embodiment of the theme of the Khojaly tragedy on the theater stages. The play “Unknown Woman” staged in the Istanbul theater is analyzed, the author and director of which is our compatriot Aygun Hasanoglu, who lives in Turkey, as well as the performances “When the Almond Tree Blooms”, “Red Angel in Khojaly”, “Arzu and Murad”, which were staged at the Azerbaijan Theater for Young Spectators. In addition, the author notes the play “Children Who Don’t Grow Up”, staged at the Kiev Theater “Bravo”, the play “My War”, embodied on the stage of the Russian Drama Theater and other dramatic works dedicated to the Khojaly tragedy.

Key words: dramaturgy, history of the genocide, Khojaly tragedy, play, theater.

Introduction. “This world is not a place of justice and rights”. These words, which were said by Heydar Aliyev, are a living photo characterizing the world order. But the author of these words fought against injustice and unfairness until the end. His struggle continues still, and the struggle of the righteous against the unrighteous wins over the years. It should be recalled that February 26 is marked as the Khojaly Genocide Day since 1993 on Heydar Aliyev’s initiative. We are living the 31st year of our unbearable pain and boundless sorrow called Khojaly. Although years have passed since the horrors of the tragedy, its pains and horrors are not forgotten. In this regard, we are witnessing the creation of many successful examples in our dramaturgy and theater art.

The interpretation of the main material. İlham Aliyev, the head of the state, signed a decree on the 30th anniversary of the Khojaly genocide on January 28, 2022. This means that the Khojaly theme of theaters should not be limited to the month of February, creative teams have the opportunity to implement initiatives on this theme throughout the year.

We should mention Aygun Hasanoglu's dramaturgical work among such initiatives. The Karabakh War and the Khojaly Genocide are the main themes in Aygun Hasanoglu's literary work, who has dedicated her life to the fight against Armenian fascism since her youth. A.Hasanoglu is the writer who wrote the Khojaly genocide for the first time, and she is the only writer who found the courage to write about the war in the middle of the war. Aygun Hasanoglu's dramaturgy describes the Karabakh war with all its horrors and contains extremely impressive scenes of the war that shake the human heart and soul.

The author's play "Adsiz gadin" ("Unknown Woman") [1], which reflects the horrors of the Khojaly genocide and is dedicated to the women who were victims of terrorism and war in the world, is staged by the creative team of the Istanbul Azerbaijan Theater every year starting from 2016. The production director of the play is Elchin Imanov, the leading role is Kamala Nabibeyli. The director combines the main essence of the work with acting and his own interpretation, presenting the theme of genocide in accordance with the theater aesthetics.

Within the framework of the international campaign "Justice to Khojaly!", the play "Khojalyda girmizi melek" ("Red Angel in Khojaly"), which was organized by the Italian organization "Associazione Arci Bellezza" and staged at the State Theater of Young Spectators in 2016, was also successful. The main idea of the new play is the bitter fate of the young girl who was captivated during the tragedy, the pure feelings, psychological and spiritual condition of the people who live refugee life. Sabuhi Mammadli is the screenwriter of the play, which attracts attention for Italian theater actors' talented performance, and Nihad Isa is the production director. Azerbaijani and Italian music was used in the play-elegy.

The premiere of the play "Badam aghaji chichekleyende" ("When the Almond Tree Blooms"), which was directed by Gulnar Hajiyeva and staged by the creative team of the Theater of Young Spectators at the Academic National Drama Theater on February 22, 2018, was welcomed with great interest.

It is no coincidence that the play was called “When the Almond Tree Blooms”. Because the almond tree is the first tree to bloom. The almond flower depicted in the logo of the “Justice to Khojaly!” campaign reflects the hope that justice will be provided for the genocide committed by Armenians in Khojaly on the night of February 25-26, 1992, and that such cruel acts will not be repeated.

Another artistic manifestation of hope for justice was the play “Boyumeyen ushaglar” (“Children Who Don’t Grow Up”) dedicated to the tragedy of 25 children who lost both their parents as a result of the Khojaly Genocide, organized by Ukraine’s “Black Square” improvisation theater and staged at Kyiv’s “Bravo” theater in 2019.

The Azerbaijan State Academic Opera and Ballet Theater hosted the play “Children Who Don’t Grow Up” in February 2022, which is based on the book of the same name by Elshad Eyvazli. The head of the project is Hikmet Javadov, the author of the idea is Murad Jafarov, and the production director is Yuriy Klyatskin.

The war and its pains met with the audience in monodrama called “Menim savashim” (“My War”) [7] by a woman on the stage of the Academic Russian Drama Theater on February 25, 2022. The author-performer of the stage work is Aleksandra Nikushina, the production director is Alexander Sharovsky.

The Irevan State Azerbaijan Drama Theater named after Jafar Jabbarli, which has persistently fought against the pain of Armenian vandalism throughout 140-year history, has organized four plays on the theme of the Khojaly genocide. The interesting stage design, the music collection accompanied with tense melodies, the emotional acting, which were in line with the dynamics of the plot line to convey the horrors of the tragedy to the audience, in the spectacle “Olum hesreti” (“Longing for Death”) [3] based on the play of the same name by the writer-playwright Sabir Shahtakht, who reflected the drama of an Azerbaijani woman’s life who was mercilessly tortured in the Armenian captivity, made watching the performance in one breath. The play “Longing for Death” conveyed to the audience that Armenian executioners infected our prisoners deliberately in order to spread terrible diseases in Azerbaijan. The plays “Longing for Death” and “Soygirim tarixinin dastani” (“Epic of Genocide History”) [3] are the neatest answers to the false “Armenian genocide” claims.

The second play of the Irevan Azerbaijan Drama Theater is the play-composition “Justice to Khojaly” based on the poem “Khojaly shehidim Shohret Hasanov” (“Khojaly Martyr Shohrat Hasanov”) [4] by the poetess-playwright Azade Taleh. The play is in the form of “mystical ritual”, and talks about Armenian barbarism and Armenian vandalism. The production director of the composition is Nijat Mirzazadeh.

Another performance of the Irevan Azerbaijan Drama Theater is Sevinj Elsever’s “Ureyinde arzu tut” (“Make a Wish”) directed by the chief director of the theater Sarvar Aliyev. This play was also staged at Azerbaijan State Theater of Young Spectators and Mingachevir Drama Theater under the name “Arzu and Murad”.

Another work of the Azerbaijan State Theater of Young Spectators dedicated to the anniversary of the Khojaly tragedy was the play “Yarimchig galmish” (“Unfinished”) [5].

With the support of the Ministry of Culture and the invitation of our embassy in Poland, the State Pantomime Theater, which has a unique place and value in the theater world of Azerbaijan, presented one of the most interesting works in its repertoire – Bakhtiyar Khanizade’s play “Khojaly bu olub” (“What happened in Khojaly” on the 30th anniversary of the Khojaly tragedy.

Sumgayit State Drama Theater commemorated the Khojaly victims with the play “Missiya” (“Mission”) [1] by the People’s artist Firudin Maharramov’s presentation.

The tragedy of Khojaly was widely highlighted in the theaters of the brotherly Republic of Turkey.

The premiere of the play “Jehennemde 8 gun” (“8 Days in Hell”) [6] took place at Gultepe Cultural Center in Istanbul in 2020. Kamala Kamal, the head of the Turkey-Azerbaijan Vision Theater, was the leading actor. The author of the play, which is based on Khojaly resident Durdane Aghayeva’s memories, is Aygun Hasanoglu, and the director is Kamran Dadashzadeh. The play was organized within the framework of the “One nation, two states” project. Actors from both countries took part in the play, which tells the story of a woman who was captivated by Armenians during the Khojaly genocide and lived in captivity for eight days.

The anniversaries of the Khojaly genocide, which is the bitterest page of our blood memory, were held in different countries of the world with the participation of our diplomatic missions, diaspora organizations and public institutions.

The largest event on the eve of the anniversary of the tragedy was organized in Berlin, the capital of Germany on February 22, 2020. Pan-European Karabakh rally was held near the Brandenburg gates in the city on the initiative of diaspora organizations operating in about 30 countries and organized by the Alliance of German Azerbaijanis. The participants of the action demanded a legal and political assessment at the international level for the genocide committed by Armenians in Khojaly 28 years ago, and to put pressure on Armenia to return the occupied Azerbaijani lands.

Conclusion. We should mention the event “My Heart Khojaly” at the Baku Congress Center organized by the Youth Fund of the Republic of Azerbaijan among domestic events in 2020. A shadow theatrical performance about the genocide was presented by the world-famous TEULIS theater in the artistic part of the “My Heart Khojaly” [6] event. The scene, which was accompanied by the music of the composition “Khojaly-613” by the French composer Pierre Thilloy, described the horrors that happened on the night of the genocide and the impact of this tragedy on the hopes and destinies of thousands of people.

Today, there is a moral front called “Justice to Khojaly!”, which calls humanity to fight for the fate of millions of people who suffer from oppression and torture as a result of terrorism. As long as there is terror, cruelty and war, this ideological front will always live.

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Nərminə Ağayeva (Azərbaycan)

XOCALI FACİƏSİ MÖVZUSU TEATR SƏHNƏSİNDƏ

Məqalədə Xocalı faciəsi mövzusunun teatr səhnələrində təcəssümü təhlil edilir. İstanbul teatrında oynanılan, Türkiyədə yaşayan həmyerlimiz Aygün Həsənoğlunun müəllifi və rejissoru olduğu “Adsız qadın”, Azərbaycan Dövlət Gənc Tamaşaçıları Teatrında səhnələşdirilən “Badam ağacı çiçəkləyəndə”, “Xocalıda qırmızı mələk”, “Arzu və Murad” tamaşaları, Kiyevin “Bravo” teatrında hazırlanan “Böyüməyən uşaqlar”, Rus Dram Teatrının “Mənim sa-vaşım” və Xocalı faciəsinə həsr olunan digər tamaşalar araşdırılır.

Açar sözlər: dramaturgiya, soyqırımı tarixi, Xocalı faciəsi, tamaşa, teatr.

Нармина Агаева (Азербайджан)

ТЕМА ХОДЖАЛИНСКОЙ ТРАГЕДИИ НА ТЕАТРАЛЬНОЙ СЦЕНЕ

Предметом рассмотрения статьи стало воплощение темы Ходжалинской трагедии на театральных сценах. Анализируется поставленный в стамбульском театре спектакль «Безымянная женщина», автором и режиссером которого является наша соотечественница Айгюн Гасаноглу, проживающая в Турции, а также спектакли «Когда цветет миндаль», «Красный ангел в Ходжалы», «Арзу и Мурад», постановка которых осуществлена в Азербайджанском Театре юного зрителя. Кроме того, автор отмечает спектакль «Дети, которые не растут», поставленный в Киевском театре «Браво», спектакль «Моя война», воплощенный на сцене Русского драматического театра и другие драматические произведения, посвященные Ходжалинской трагедии.

Ключевые слова: драматургия, история геноцида, Ходжалинская трагедия, спектакль, театр.